

Press Release

Z-ONA4LIFE granted as an EU Green Week Partner Event

Gijon, ES, May 30, 2025 – This year, the Z-ONA4LIFE project is going to be part of the EU Green Week, with its workshop on **Driving Circular Economy through end-of-waste status and zeolite innovation**.

The EU Green Week is an annual event organised by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Environment. It serves as Europe's leading environmental conference, aiming to raise awareness, promote, and discuss European environmental policy. Important to attract policymakers, businesses, researchers & eco-activists, and other stakeholders from across Europe and beyond, it identifies every year a different theme, in order to converge efforts in a factual roadmap.

This year's theme is "Circular Solutions for a Competitive EU", focusing on how Europe can transition from traditional linear models of production and consumption to more circular and sustainable practices.

The EU Green Week 2025

The kick-off of the GREEN WEEK is taking place from 3 to 5 June 2025 in Brussels with stakeholders and high-level policy discussion, and throughout the entire month, over 300 partner events will take place across Europe, engaging communities and bringing discussions and novelties about the circular economy.

Z-ona4life this year is engaging the audience with a workshop which explores how synthetic zeolites from waste, support circular economy practices by reducing industrial waste and improving resource efficiency.

Drawing from the [Z-ONA4LIFE Blueprint](#), policy recommendations, industrial applications, and strategies will be analysed, with the aim of achieving end-of-waste status to accelerate waste-based zeolite adoption across Europe. The identified targeted audience represents policymakers, industry professionals, sustainability experts, researchers, and circular economy stakeholders.

The **Workshop Agenda** is [available here](#)

[Register and secure your spot](#)

More information about the [event is available on the Green Week website](#)

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Available material for the press

[Image to use for the Press Release](#)

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